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Career Development And Work Environment On Creativity Of Catholic Secondary Schools In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the career development and work environment on creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State. The sub-objectives were to: Assess the relationship of career development and the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State; Examine the relationship of work environment and the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State. This study is anchored on Kanter's theory of Empowerment. Data were generated through primary and secondary sources. The method for data collection was the questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of the catholic secondary school. The population of the study was four thousand five hundred and eighty-seven (4587). A sample of 882 respondents was drawn from the population by Boig and Gall (1973) formula. Eight hundred and seventy three (873) copies of the questionnaire were retrieved and this represents 98.9% of the total sample size. The hypotheses were tested using correlation analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. Findings from the study revealed that; Career development has significant positive relationship with the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State $T=13.477$, $p=0.000$; Work environment has significant positive relationship with the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State, $T=12.412$, $p=0.000$; Staff Recognition has significant positive relationship with the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State, $T=4.682$, $p=0.006$. The study recommended that The study recommends that, Management should encourage on collaborative decision making and problem solving, geared towards Career development. Since the environment is an indispensable tool in management, it should not be taken with kids' glove as it can influence the organization to achieve its stipulated objectives from time to time. Management should publicly recognize the efforts of their employees to induce their performance in the work place. Workers promotion and promotion arrears (intrinsic reward) should be implemented as at when due.

Keywords: career development, work environment, creativity, catholic secondary schools, creativity

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The success and survival of catholic secondary depends upon the performance and satisfaction of their teachers and hence the social institution has to meet their demands in order to retain their talent. The lack of growth and development is highlighted as the most discussed cause of the high turnover rate globally, particularly in the educational sector (Atueyi, & Mbanefo 2025). Research highlights that the management of educational sector still focuses on old traditional methods to retain employees, i.e., one-way communication and feedback, where employees cannot share their long-term plans with their respective bosses and cannot get feedback or suggestions for their career development. In view of the 21st

century, such methods are no longer effective to reduce the employee turnover rate (Nwangwu, Ohanyere, Nwangwu, & Atueyi, (2025).

Low morale and motivation, If teachers and staff feel disconnected from the mission and values of the school, they may experience lower morale and lack of motivation to perform their best. Limited professional development opportunities, without access to ongoing training and development opportunities, employees may feel stagnant in their roles and disengaged from their work. Inadequate recognition and appreciation, Employees thrive on recognition and appreciation for their hard work and contributions. Without proper acknowledgment, they may feel undervalued and disengaged (Ifechukwu-jacobs, & Atueyi, 2024). Lack of collaboration and teamwork, When there is a lack of collaboration and teamwork among the staff, it can create a disconnected and fragmented work environment that hinders employee engagement. Addressing these problems requires a focused effort on improving communication, providing professional development opportunities, recognizing and appreciating employees' contributions, and fostering a culture of collaboration and teamwork (Ifechukwu-Jacobs, Arinze, & Nwangwu, & Atueyi, 2025).. Schools can also consider implementing regular feedback mechanisms, promoting a positive work-life balance, and aligning staff goals with the school's mission and values to enhance employee engagement. It is upon this backdrop that this study is undertaken to evaluate the employee engagement and performance of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine employee engagement and performance of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State. This study specifically identified the following objectives to:

- i. Assess the relationship of career development and the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State
- ii. Examine the relationship of work environment and the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State
- iii. Examine the relationship of staff recognition and the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State

1.3 Statement of Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated

Ho₁: Career development has no significant positive relationship with the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State.

Ho₂: Work environment has no significant positive relationship with the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State.

Ho₃: Staff recognition has no positive relationship with the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Career Development

Career development is perceived as a joint effort between the individual employee and the organization. Career development describes the lifelong process of managing life, learning and work. It involves individuals planning and making decisions about education, training and career choices as well as developing the right skills and knowledge to do this (Arthur et al, 2015). Greenhaus et al, (2015) sought to investigate the relationship between talent management and succession planning processes. The study, which was carried out using descriptive and inferential statistics revealed that talent management and succession planning within government organizations met the requirements and therefore impacted on talent absorption, talent retention and talent development which gave the organizations a competitive edge (Onya, Arinze, & Atueyi, (2025).

Career development is the lifelong process of managing learning, work, leisure, and transitions in order to move toward a personally determined and evolving preferred future (Armstrong, 2009). Career development is defined as “an ongoing, formalized effort by an organisation that focuses on developing

and enriching the organization's human resources in light of both the employees' and the organization's needs" (Byars and Rue, 2014). McDougall and Vaughn (2017) argue that "career development involves aligning individual subjective and more objective career aspects of an organization to find a match between individual and organizational needs, personal characteristics and career roles." This author views career development as a mutual role, based on the needs and circumstances of both individuals and organizations.

2.1.2 Work Environment

Work environment according to Ukeje (2012) encompasses all those factors within and outside that affect an industry's operation and it includes the following variables customers, competitors, suppliers, industry trends, regulations, other forms of government activities, social, economic and technological factors. By this, it means that no business operates in an environment where it constantly interacts with these internal and external forces. Robbin (2017) asserts that environment of business is very important not only as a determinant of structure but a factor that must be harnessed by organizations to ensure overall organizational effectiveness.

Earnest, Agbo and Odigbo (2017) perceive work environment as factors outside the control of business that influence its objectives, functioning, strategies and the entire performance of organization in an area. They further classified business environment into internal and external environments. Internal environment of business hinges on human activities like production, extraction or marketing and includes man, money, machinery, materials and management (5Ms). External work environment of business are variables that a firm acts and reacts to outside the business which affect implementation and profitability of the business. External work environment may be subdivided into micro and macro environment. Micro environment is the crucial environment in the immediate ambience of the business known also as the operating environment. This according to Ohanyere Arinze, & Atueyi (2025) maintain that the variables that affect the capacity of the business to work smoothly are suppliers, intermediaries, competitors, consumers and the public. Macro environments are those factors that may create both opportunity and threat to the business which may be economic and / or non economic.

2.1.3 Staff Recognition

Staff Recognition is the demonstration of appreciation for a level of performance, an achievement or a contribution to achieve a set goal or objective. It can be confidential or public, causal or formal. It is always in addition to pay" (Okwudili, 2015). In addition to reward, employees also need recognition. Individuals like to share their achievements with others and have it recognized and celebrated. When this need is satisfied, it works as an excellent motivator. If employers rely on salary alone to recognize contribution and achievement it is most possible that the employee's objective will become modified to secure the pay and nothing more and this in turn will lead to a degraded culture of the organization. When used correctly recognition is a cost-effective way of enhancing achievements and enable people to feel involved in the company culture (Pitts 2014). Recognition helps to spark up the creative ability of employees which makes them put in their best to achieve organizational goals and objectives.

Also, important correlation was reported to exist between recognition and employee satisfaction, work morale, and productivity; the study also reveals that employees who are satisfied with their company's recognition and appreciation programs tend to be more significantly satisfied with their jobs, feels more valued at work and are more likely to remain committed with the organization (Salah, 2016).

2.1.4 Creativity

Creativity has been identified as one of the most distinct of human attributes. It is indeed a special case of problem solving in which originality is emphasized (Achor, 2014). Creativity is marked by the ability to create, bring into existence, to invent into a new form, to produce through imaginative skill, to make to bring into existence something new. Creativity is the ability to generate new knowledge by expanding and transforming the vision of reality as the future that can systematically organize its activities, this is a creative construction. Creativity assumes a creative approach in designing new object properties using already existing elements (properties, relationships). The term "creativity" is closer to the original meaning of the word "constructiveness". It can be described as having the quality of something created

rather than imitated so being creative is nothing but having the passion of creating new and unique ideas or concepts.

Creativity is not ability to create out of nothing, but the ability to generate new ideas by combining, changing or reapplying existing ideas. Some creative ideas are astonishing and brilliant, while others are just simple, good practical ideas that no one seems to have thought of yet (Harris, 2018). Everyone has substantial creative ability irrespective of age, class, gender or race. Creativity is also an attitude, the ability to accept change and newness, a willingness to play with ideas and possibilities, a flexibility of outlook, the habit of enjoying the good, while looking for ways to improve it, we are socialized into accepting only a small number of permissible or normal things (Okpara, 2017). Creativity is a process by which a symbolic domain in the culture is changed. New songs, new ideas, new machines are what creativity is about Mihaly (2017). Creativity is the ability to make or otherwise bring into existence something new, whether a new solution to a problem, a new method or device, or a new artistic object or form. Wyckoff (2011) as noted in Okpara (2017) views creativity as new and useful. Creativity is the act of seeing things that everyone around us sees while making connections that no one else has made. Creativity is moving from the known to the unknown (Okpara, 2017).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Kanter's theory of Empowerment

Kanter (1993) defined empowerment as the ability of an individual to independently make decisions and utilize available resources to accomplish the necessary goals. She postulates that if an organization is structured to provide empowerment and access to job-related empowerment opportunities, the structure will have a positive impact on employees and their performance to work. Alternatively, an organizational structure that does not provide empowerment and access to job-related empowerment opportunities will have a negative impact on the employees and their performance at work.

Kanter (1993) posits that in an empowerment-structured organization there is increased autonomy, job satisfaction, and performance among employees. Consequently, feelings of burnout and job stress will decrease, and the result is employee performance. Kanter stated that the work environment structures and perceived employee access to power and opportunity structures is related to employee attitudes and behaviors in an organization. Kanter believed that employees display attitudes based on the presence of perceived power and opportunities. According to Kanter, there exist four work empowerment structures: access to information, resources, support, and opportunity. Access to information refers to the data, technical knowledge, and expertise needed for job performance.

Access to resources refers to the ability to obtain needed supplies, materials, money and personnel to meet established organizational goals. Access to support refers to the guidance, feedback, and direction provided by supervisors, peers, and subordinates. Access to opportunity refers to the growth, mobility and the chance to build upon knowledge base (Kanter, 1993). Kanter believed that if employees within an organization perceive opportunities for success is present, the employees' attitude, job satisfaction, and overall employee performance will be enhanced. In order for an employee to perceive that opportunity exists, the employee must be in a position that allows access to resources, information, and support. Empowerment is achieved by identifying organizational policies and practices that foster a sense of powerlessness and implementing strategies and tactics that can be used to remove them.

Based on this premise fronted by the Kater's theory on empowerment and organization performance, the study postulates that when employees are able to access the constructs of structural empowerment within their organizations: access to support, opportunity, resources and information they will be committed to their roles within their organizations. Kanter believed that if employees within an organization perceive opportunities for success is present, the employees' attitude, job satisfaction, and overall organizational performance will be enhanced. In order for an employee to perceive that opportunity exists, the employee must be in a position that allows access to resources, information, and support (Seibert, Gang & Stephen, 2011).

2.3 Empirical Review

Ikeagu, Odira, & Anah. (2023). examined effect of employee retention strategies on organizational performance of mission secondary schools in Onitsha Archdiocese, Anambra State. This study is anchored on Equity theory of motivation, developed in the early 1960's by John Stacey Adams. The study adopted survey method of research. Percentage tables were used to analyse the questionnaire, while regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses of the study. Data were generated through primary and secondary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of the selected firm. The population of the study was 1745, the sample size of the study were three hundred and thirty-five (335) using Borg and Gall Formula while Three hundred and twenty-three (323) were retrieved. The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed, Flexible schedule has significant impact on organizational performance of teachers in mission secondary schools in Onitsha Archdiocese of Anambra, $T=3.511$, $p=0.000$, Work environment has significant impact on organizational performance of teachers in mission secondary schools in Onitsha Archdiocese of Anambra. $T=2.899$, $p=0.008$, Recognition has significant impact on organizational performance of teachers in mission secondary schools in Onitsha Archdiocese of Anambra, $T=4.468$, $p=0.000$. the study concludes that employee retention strategies has significant positive effect on organizational performance of mission secondary schools in Onitsha Archdiocese.

Ntadom, Atueyi and Jacobs (2021) examined the effect of career development on organizational performance, a Study of selected higher institution in Anambra State Nigeria. The study was anchored on Self-concept theory of career development. As a cross-sectional survey the research design were used, a structured questionnaire instrument were developed and used for data collection by the researcher to which reflect such options as strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree, which is popularly referred as five (5) points likert scale. It was used to obtain information from the respondents. The population of the study comprised of 57, 710 students selected across the five south east states of Nigeria. A sample size of 399 students was drawn from the population, using Taro Yamane formular of which three hundred and forty-seven (347) copies of questionnaires were duly completed and returned; showing 96% response rate. Research hypotheses were tested using ANOVA regression analysis which was carried out with the aid of Statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 23. The study found that career development has significant effect on Organizational Performance. In view of the findings, the study recommended that Training should be done on collaborative decision making and problem solving, geared towards decentralization; Employees should be trained according to the present content of the environment. The reason is that training implies acquiring knowledge to fill the gap between what is known and what should be known

Shimelis and Mahesh (2021) examined the impact of the working environment on the organizational performance of the the Arjo Dedessa Sugar Factory (ADSF) and Finchaa Sugar Factory (FSF) in Ethiopia, the physical working environment, work-related risks and injuries, and the psychological working environment and social work environment. The total number of employees in the two sectors is 867 and 2824, respectively. Selected samples of 266 and 338 employees were used as stratified random samples to investigate work-related environmental conditions. A response rate of 60% was achieved. The statistical software SPSS V 23.0 was used to analyze and to determine the relationship between the dependent and independent variables using Pearson's correlation and linear regression analysis. The results show that ADSF employees have a more modest social work environment than FSF employees, but the physical work environment of both organizations contributes the least. Both the ADSF and FSF physical working environments had a statistically significant impact on performance. Improvements in the social environment have been proposed to improve the psychological health of employees. The result is ADSF organization performance = $0.173 + 0.250$ physical work environment + 0.304 administrative work environment. FSF Organization Performance = $0.157 + 0.355$ Social working Environment.

Dian and Aslam (2021) analyzed a impact empowerment of employees, organizational justice, conflict and work motivation on employee performance through case studies Mandiri Branch Office (KCP) Social

Security Bank in Jakarta, Indonesia. This study adopted a causal research design and data collection methods by conducting a questionnaire survey of 41 respondents. The sampling technique is intended is a sampling technique is saturated. The analytical tool intended is SPSS version 21. The results show that some employee authorization, organizational justice, and work motivation are related to impact positively d's significant to employees performance. At the same time, conflict has a partial negative impact on employee performance and is not significant. In addition, employee empowerment, organizational justice, conflict and work motivation also have a significant impact on employee performance.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive survey approach. The uses of descriptive statistics was applied because of its capability to summarize large quantities of data using measures in form of graphical and numerical techniques (Burns, 2000).

3.2 Sources of Data

With respect to this study, the researcher made use of primary and secondary sources of data collection. The primary sources of data collection include the questionnaire; while the secondary sources of data collection includes the journals, magazines, textbooks and internet.

3.3 Population of the Study

The target population of this study was limited to the number of teaching staff at catholic secondary school in Anambra state. The population comprised 4587 employees working in Anambra state.

3.4: Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Given the nature of this study, it will be difficult to cover the entire population of **4587**. A fair representative sample of the population was therefore considered imperative. Accordingly, the sample size for the study was determined by using the Borg & Gall (1973) formular for calculating sample size as follows:

$$n = (Z_x)^2(e) [N]$$

$$(Z_x)^2 = 1.960$$

$$e = \text{Error of margin (0.05)}$$

$$N = \text{Population of Interest =}$$

$$X = \text{Significance Level}$$

$$n = (1.960)^2 (0.05) [4587]$$

$$n = (1.960)^2 (0.05) [4587]$$

$$n = (3.8461) (229.35)$$

$$= 882.1030$$

$$n = 882$$

Thus, the sample size is 882 staff of secondary schools academic staff in Anambra State. This study employed a random sampling technique in selecting academic staff based on factors such as time available for data collection, accessibility, and willingness to participate in the study.

3.5 Instrument for Data Collection

A structured instrument (questionnaire) was designed to reflect the popular five (5) point Likert scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree, strongly disagree and undecided. The questionnaire contained close-ended statements, which were used to get the views and opinions of respondents on employee engagement and performance of catholic schools in Anambra State..

3.6 Method of Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using quantitative data, analysis methods. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation was used to present quantitative data in form of tables. Data from questionnaire was coded and entered into the computer using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS Version 21) for analysis.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Test Of Statement Of Hypotheses

Hypothesis one: Ho₃: Career development has no significant positive relationship with the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State.

Correlations						CRT	CAD	
Spearman's rho	CRT	Correlation Coefficient				1.000	.503**	
		Sig. (2-tailed)				.	.000	
		N				873	873	
		Bootstrap ^b	Bias				.000	-.001
			Std. Error				.000	.028
			BCa 95% Confidence Interval		Lower		.	.445
		Upper			.	.554		
	CAD	Correlation Coefficient				.503**	1.000	
		Sig. (2-tailed)				.000	.	
		N				873	873	
		Bootstrap ^b	Bias				-.001	.000
			Std. Error				.028	.000
			BCa 95% Confidence Interval		Lower		.445	.
		Upper			.554	.		

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

b. Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 873 bootstrap samples

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Mean	Lower			
Pair 1	CRT - CAD	.52692	1.15517	.03910	.45018	.60365	13.477	872	.000

Table 1 indicates the relationship between the independent variable career development (CAD) and the dependent variable Creative (CRT). At a 0.05 level of significant, 95% confidence level interval ranging between 0.554 and 603 at the upper case, and also 0.445 and 0.450 at the lower case, with a 2 tailed test of sample distribution showing the critical area in a distribution. The spearman correlation coefficient shows a value of 0.50%, which shows a high correlation coefficient between the dependent and independent variable. This further portrays the high goodness of fit of the model

Model 1= $CAD = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CRT + \mu$

Table 1 indicates the difference in mean value (.52692) and standard deviation (1.15517) for the extent of relationship that existed between the variables included in the group. The single group variables in model two of the hypotheses are represented by CAD & CRT (Career development and creativity).

However, the paired sample t-test showed that creativity level increased significantly when the perceived career development was adopted. A t-test value of career development is said to be significantly high when it is above or equal 2 (t-value > 2.00), but when the t-value is less than 2.00 (t-value < 2.00), it is concluded that the variables within the paired sample has no significant relationship. In conclusion to this result, the t-value was obtained at 13.477 which is significant high. The study therefore concluded that there is a significantly high positive relationship between Career development and creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State.

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, otherwise, reject.

Decision: We reject the null hypothesis, since the p-value is 0.000** which is less than the critical value 0.05, this study reveals that career development has significant positive relationship with the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Work environment has no significant positive relationship with the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State.

				CRT	WRKE	
Spearman's rho	CRT	Correlation Coefficient		1.000	.528**	
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.	.000	
		N		873	873	
		Bootstrap ^b	Bias		.000	.000
			Std. Error		.000	.030
			BCa 95% Confidence Interval	Lower	.	.468
	Upper	.		.584		
	WRKE	Correlation Coefficient		.528**	1.000	
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.	
		N		873	873	
		Bootstrap ^b	Bias		.000	.000
			Std. Error		.030	.000
BCa 95% Confidence Interval			Lower	.468	.	
	Upper	.584	.			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

b. Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 873 bootstrap samples

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	CRT - WRKE	.48912	1.16433	.03941	.41177	.56646	12.412	872	.000

Table 2 indicates the relationship between the independent variable work environment (WRKE) and the dependent variable creativity (CRT). At a 0.05 level of significant, 95% confidence level interval ranging between 0.584 and 0.566 at the upper case, and also 0.468 and 0.411 at the lower case, with a 2 tailed test of sample distribution showing the critical area in a distribution. The spearman correlation coefficient shows a value of 0.52%, which shows a high correlation coefficient between the dependent and independent variable. This further portrays the high goodness of fit of the model

Model 2= $CRT = \beta_0 + \beta_1WRKE + \mu$

Table 2 indicates the difference in mean value (.48912) and standard deviation (1.16433) for the extent of relationship that existed between the variables included in the group. The single group variables in model two of the hypotheses are represented by WRKE & CRT (Work environment and creativity).

However, the paired sample t-test showed that creativity level increased significantly when the perceived Work environment was adopted. A t-test value of Work environment is said to be significantly high when it is above or equal 2 (t-value > 2.00), but when the t-value is less than 2.00 (t-value < 2.00), it is concluded that the variable within the paired sample has no significant relationship. In conclusion to this result, the t-value was obtained at 12.412 which is significant high. The study therefore concluded that there is a significantly high positive relationship between Work environment and creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State.

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, otherwise, reject.

Decision: We reject the null hypothesis, since the p-value is 0.000** which is less than the critical value 0.05, this study reveals that work environment has significant positive relationship with the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State

Hypothesis Three

Ho₃: Staff recognition has no positive relationship with the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State.

		Correlations		
			CRT	STR
Spearman's rho	CRT	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.780**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
	N	873	873	
	Bootstrap ^b	Bias	.000	.000
		Std. Error	.000	.032
		BCa 95% Confidence Interval		
		Lower	.	.518
	Upper	.	.742	

STR	Correlation Coefficient	.780**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
	N	873	873
Bootstrap ^b	Bias	.000	.000
	Std. Error	.032	.000
BCa 95% Confidence Interval	Lower	.518	.
	Upper	.742	.

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

b. Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 873 bootstrap samples

Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower				Upper
Pair 1	CRT - STR	.21764	1.37334	.04648	.30887	.42641	4.682	872	.000

Table 3 indicates the relationship between the independent variable staff recognition (STR) and the dependent variable creativity (ECS). At a 0.05 level of significant, 95% confidence level interval ranging between 0.742 and 0.426 at the upper case, and also 0.518 and 0.308 at the lower case, with a 2 tailed test of sample distribution showing the critical area in a distribution. The spearman correlation coefficient shows a value of 0.780%, which shows a high correlation coefficient between the dependent and independent variable. This further portrays the high goodness of fit of the model

Model 3= $CRT = \beta_0 + \beta_1STR + \mu$

Table 3 indicates the difference in mean value (.21764) and standard deviation (1.37334) for the extent of relationship that existed between the variables included in the group. The single group variables in model two of the hypotheses are represented by STR & CRT (Staff recognition and creativity).

However, the paired sample t-test showed that creativity level increased significantly when the perceived staff recognition was adopted. A t-test value of staff recognition is said to be significantly high when it is above or equal 2 (t-value > 2.00), but when the t-value is less than 2.00 (t-value < 2.00), it is concluded that the variable within the paired sample has no significant relationship. In conclusion to this result, the t-value was obtained at 4.682 which is significant high. The study therefore concluded that there is a significantly high positive relationship between Staff recognition and creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State.

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, otherwise, reject.

Decision: We reject the null hypothesis, since the p-value is 0.000** which is less than the critical value 0.05, this study reveals that Staff recognition has positive relationship with the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study found that Career development has significant positive relationship with the creativity of catholic secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that career development and creativity are important aspects of personal and professional growth that can be mutually beneficial. Engaging in career development activities, such as obtaining new skills and knowledge, can expand one's creativity by providing new experiences, perspectives, and ideas. Similarly, cultivating creativity in one's career can lead to more innovative and

adaptive problem-solving, which can be a valuable asset in today's fast-paced and ever-changing job market. Moreover, many career paths, such as entrepreneurship, design, and technology, require a high degree of creativity. The study found that work environment has a positive significant effect on performance of catholic secondary schools in Anambra state. The findings imply that A healthy and supportive work environment can have a profound impact on creativity. An environment that encourages collaboration, innovation, and risk-taking can foster a culture of creativity, allowing employees to experiment with new ideas and approaches. This can be achieved through practices such as providing a diverse and inclusive workplace, fostering open communication, encouraging experimentation and failure, and providing resources and opportunities for employee development. Conversely, a negative or toxic work environment, characterized by excessive competition, lack of support, or micromanagement, can stifle creativity and undermine employee morale and productivity. The study recommends that, Management should encourage on collaborative decision making and problem solving, geared towards Career development. Since the environment is an indispensable tool in management, it should not be taken with kids' glove as it can influence the organization to achieve its stipulated objectives from time to time. Management should publicly recognize the efforts of their employees to induce their performance in the work place. Workers promotion and promotion arrears (intrinsic reward) should be implemented as at when due.

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